

ECO STP 2023

6th IWA International Conference
on **eco-Technologies for
Wastewater Treatment**

GIRONA- SPAIN
26th-29th June

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

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Following the previous successful IWA ecoSTP conferences (Spain 2012, Italy 2014, UK 2016, Canada 2018, Italy 2021), it is our great pleasure to welcome you to the 6th IWA International Conference on eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment to be held from June 26th to 29th, 2023 in Girona.

ecoSTP-23 aims to discuss the latest cutting-edge eco-technologies for a sustainable transition in wastewater treatment, reuse, and resource recovery, at urban and industrial scale, giving special attention to the efficient transfer of knowledge into practice. Building a more resilient future for water management needs a transdisciplinary and multi-domain examination, including socio-economic and governance aspects. ecoSTP23 will include hydro-social aspects and the multiple factors that currently frame water management.

Maite Pijuan and Ignasi Rodriguez-Roda

Co-chairs of ecoSTP23

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Isle Utilities (United Kingdom)
Navigating towards an innovative and
sustainable water industry

Gustaf Olsson
Lund University (Sweden)
Water - key indicator of global
warming and basis for energy and
food production

Krishna Pagilla
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PROGRAM

Application of electrocoagulation treatment to meat industry wastewater

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Abstract

In recent years, a large number of researchers believe that electrocoagulation (EC) treatment has a future in wastewater treatment. In this work, we investigate the possibility of applying the EC process for the purification of meat industry wastewater. The experimental removal efficiencies for COD, BOD, total P, total N, and turbidity were 46%, 50%, 95%, 97%, and 99%, for aluminum electrodes and for iron electrodes removal efficiencies were 48%, 52%, 94%, 99%, and 98%, respectively. The next step is to optimize and improve the treatment to obtain water as a product that we can use for irrigating the surrounding agricultural areas or for reuse in the production process, which is very important from the point of view of the circular economy.

Keywords

wastewater, electrocoagulation, water reuse

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two sets of the EC experiments have been performed: (1) two aluminum electrodes Al(-)/Al(+)(EC1), (2) two iron electrodes Fe(+)/Fe(-) (EC2). The treatments were done in an EC unit which was made of borosilicate glass with a volume of 600 ml. For treatments aluminum and iron electrodes with the same dimensions of 10 cm x 5 cm x 0.1 cm were used. During the treatments the distance between the electrodes were 3 cm, the current strength were 3.33 mA/cm², the rotation speed were 280/min, the surface of the immersed electrodes were 30 cm², with the treatment time were 1 hour, and the volume of treated water was 0.5 l. The raw meat industry wastewater was characterized before and after each EC treatment determined: chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), total phosphorous (P), total nitrogen (N), pH, and turbidity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effects of electrocoagulation on meat industry wastewater were present in Table 1. To assess the effects of EC determining the pH value is the most appropriate step. Based on the obtained results, it is observed that the pH value increased by ~1 pH unit. We can explain this by a significant amount of ion OH⁻ released by the electrochemical reaction of the hydrolysis of water at the cathode. The change in pH during EC was also observed by other researchers (Tahreem et al., 2020). The experimental removal efficiencies for COD, BOD, total P, total N, and turbidity were 46%, 50%, 95%, 97%, and 99%, for aluminum electrodes and for iron electrodes removal efficiencies were 48%, 52%, 94%, 99%, and 98%, respectively. We can explain the reduction of COD, BOD, P, and N in treated water by the adsorption onto the surfaces of hydroxide precipitates, which are released by the electrodes. The high percentage of turbidity reduction is in accordance with the previously mentioned efficiencies of the tested treatments. The presented results show that there is no big difference in the achieved efficiencies between EC1 and EC2, therefore our recommendation is EC2 because Fe electrodes are cheaper.

Table 1. Parameters of wastewater characterization, before and after electrocoagulation

Parameters	E0	EC1	EC2
COD (mg O₂/l)	846	454	443
BOD (mg O₂/l)	433	215	206
Total P (mg/l)	2.26	0.12	0.14
Total N (mg N/l)	64.8	2.13	0.86
pH	6.66	7.93	7.82
Turbidity (NTU)	210	2.85	5.06

Based on the above conclusions, it can be noted that EC holds immense potential to replace conventional wastewater treatment methods. In the future, we will focus on the optimization and improvement of the treatment in order to obtain water as a product that we can use for irrigating the surrounding agricultural areas or for reuse in the production process, which is very important from the point of view of the circular economy.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, Horizon Europe - Work Programme 2021-2022 Widening participation and strengthening the European Research Area, HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02, under grant agreement No [101060110], SmartWaterTwin